

Time to Turn to Sustainability: Embracing Terroir Products from Enduring Involvement to Purchase Intention

Il est temps de se tourner vers la durabilité : de l'implication durable à l'intention d'achat dans l'adoption des produits du terroir

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Abstract

The current global situation is both critical and challenging, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable consumption to address these issues. In this context, terroir products have been recognized as a viable solution for achieving sustainability and have gained a notable position among consumers. Enduring involvement with terroir products enables consumers to assess their positive outcomes, fostering a sense of satisfaction, which in turn enhances trust in these products and strengthens purchase intention. Accordingly, this research aims to validate a conceptual framework integrating enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust, and purchase intention toward terroir products. Principal Component Analysis and Structural Equation Modeling were conducted to test the proposed model using survey data collected from 201 Tunisian consumers. The results validate the proposed model and highlight the mediating roles of satisfaction and trust in explaining purchase intention. Specifically, enduring involvement positively influences satisfaction, which subsequently enhances trust and ultimately leads to higher purchase intention. The findings reveal a sequential full mediation, with satisfaction and trust mediating the relationships in the proposed model.

Keywords: terroir product; sustainable consumption; enduring involvement; satisfaction; trust; purchase intention.

Résumé

La situation mondiale souffre de nos jours de plusieurs crises et difficultés réclamant d'urgence une consommation durable. Dans cette perspective, les produits du terroir apparaissent comme une alternative crédible favorisant la durabilité et sont valorisés par les consommateurs. L'utilisation fréquente de ces produits permet d'apprécier les effets positifs générant un sentiment de satisfaction susceptible à son tour de renforcer la confiance et, par conséquent, stimuler l'intention d'achat. La présente recherche s'attache à concevoir et valider un modèle théorique reliant implication durable, satisfaction, confiance et intention d'achat des produits du terroir. Nous avons réalisé une Analyse en Composantes Principales ainsi qu'une modélisation par Equations Structurelles afin de tester le modèle proposé. Les résultats d'une enquête menée auprès de 201 répondants tunisiens ont validé le modèle proposé. Les effets médiateurs de la confiance et de la satisfaction ont été démontrés dans l'explication de l'intention d'achat. Il ressort que l'implication durable améliore la satisfaction, laquelle accroît ensuite la confiance et conduit alors à une plus forte intention d'achat.

Mots clés : Produit du terroir ; consommation durable ; l'implication durable ; la satisfaction ; la confiance ; l'intention d'achat.

Introduction

Living in crisis-stricken contexts, the world today is grappling with environmental and social transformations, driven by factors such as pollution, recurring food crises, scarcity of natural resources, etc. (Ioan et al., 2020; Raghuramapatruni & Enamala, 2025). These changes have influenced consumption patterns, leading to a shift toward sustainable consumption (Ghvanidze et al., 2019; Charton-Vachet et al., 2020). Sustainability aims to foster conditions that enable humans and nature to coexist harmoniously, ensuring the social and economic development of both current and future generations (Azougui & Maghnaoui, 2025; Nodehi et al., 2022). To align economic responsibilities with social and environmental expectations, the three pillars of sustainability (Mohamad Taghvaei et al., 2023), new practices have emerged to address consumers' evolving preferences. Among these practices, terroir products have become closely intertwined with the concept of sustainability (Charters et al., 2017), particularly in alignment with Sustainable Development Goal 12 on Responsible Consumption and Production (Haid et al., 2024). In fact, they have firmly integrated into consumers' diets, representing a growing trend that has evolved in recent years (Ertus & Bonescu, 2024; Maghnaoui & Touhami, 2024). They are perceived as products that guarantee authenticity, deeply tied to a specific location, a rich history, and distinct typicality (Cappeliez, 2017). The consumption of terroir products has gained attention among consumers (Couder & Valette-Florence, 2024) who are increasingly seeking products that promote sustainable development (Ghvanidze et al., 2019). They have developed a growing interest in traditional and regional products, placing significant importance on their origin. Additionally, they prioritize high-quality products crafted using local expertise and natural resources (Hammou & Lekbira, 2024). This interest has been further amplified by influencer marketing, which increasingly highlights terroir products and reinforces their authenticity, sustainability, and cultural value (Hazeb, 2025). The shift toward these products has become an international trend, with many countries gaining recognition for their superior terroir products. For example, France is renowned for its cheese (Bérard & Marchenay, 2000), Italy for its wine (Capitello et al., 2024), Tunisia for its olive oil (Dekhili et al., 2011; Damak et al., 2021), and Morocco for its dates (Housni & Machrafi, 2024a).

Adhering to terroir products goes beyond a one-time purchase; people consume these products for the values and the unique benefits they offer compared to other products (Ertus et al., 2019). Health-conscious consumers and those concerned about the environmental impact of their consumption, tend to invest more time and effort in their purchasing decisions

(Ghvanidze et al., 2019). This commitment is driven by enduring involvement, an internal psychological state that motivates consumers to constantly choose the same product. When consumers perceive the positive effects of consuming terroir products constantly on their health, they experience satisfaction with their choice (Beckman et al., 2020). This satisfaction reinforces their likelihood of repurchasing the same product to replicate those positive emotions. Over time, this sense of satisfaction fosters trust in the product (Konuk, 2018), as consumers come to view terroir products as a reliable option for safeguarding their health and ensuring the security of their food. Once people perceive that terroir products are trustworthy and beneficial to their health, this perception fosters positive intentions (Ertus & Bonescu, 2024) and may drive consumers to consider purchasing these products for their positive impacts on their lives.

Existing research on terroir products has mainly adopted a cognitive and product-centered perspective, focusing on attributes such as perceived quality, authenticity, region of origin, and product congruence. While these variables are essential, they provide only a partial understanding of consumers' purchase intention. In contrast, psychological and relational mechanisms remain relatively underexplored in the context of terroir products. This study addresses this gap by proposing a model that integrates enduring involvement as a psychological factor and satisfaction and trust as relational constructs to explain purchase intention. By shifting the focus from product attributes to consumers' psychological engagement and relational evaluation, this research offers a complementary and enriched perspective on terroir product consumption. From this perspective, the current research states the following problem: To what extent do enduring involvement, satisfaction, and trust influence and enhance consumers' purchase intentions toward terroir products? This paper aims to validate a conceptual framework integrating enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust and purchase intention of terroir products. By doing so, our research model extends prior work by validating the psychological and relational pathways through which consumers develop purchase intentions in the context of terroir products. In addition, the mediating roles of satisfaction and trust will be analysed to gain deeper insights into the process of developing purchase intention for terroir products. Also, practical recommendations will be provided to whom it may concern.

1. Terroir Products: A Catalyst for Sustainable Development

With increasing pressure to address sustainable development, companies are compelled to adopt sustainable practices. Promoting terroir products has become a means for companies to demonstrate their commitment to sustainability by emphasizing their local roots and traditional know-how—criteria that align closely with the principles of sustainable development, as terroir products are recognized as a tool for sustainable development (Bérard, 2016; Beylier & Messeghem, 2008). Sustainable consumption emphasizes a return to local and seasonal products, grounded in the principles of the circular economy (Badulescu & Moutat, 2020). According to Zindy et al. (2017), terroir products are closely related to several categories, including local products characterized by geographical proximity between production and consumption sites (Merle & Piotrowski, 2012), regional products linked to regional identity (Van Ittersum, 2007), traditional products associated with transgenerational consumption, and artisanal products known for their non-industrial production processes (Beudaert & Lambert, 2020; Vanhonacker et al., 2010). While these categories remain conceptually distinct, they share common characteristics that contribute to the perception of terroir products as offering unique and superior quality (Ertus et al., 2019). Terroir products are characterized by natural elements originating from the soil (Peng et al., 2021) and cultural traditions deeply rooted in ancestral heritage (Lenglet & Giannelloni, 2016; Cappeliez, 2017). Their specificity lies in artisanal production processes, the use of natural and premium ingredients, producers' craftsmanship and shared values, as well as the significance of the location's heritage. What makes these products unique is that the raw materials are produced and transformed within the same specific geographic area, ensuring authenticity and a strong bond to their origin (Ertus et al., 2019). Terroir products contribute to health by ensuring food security (Ertus, 2021), while also delivering broader benefits across the economy, environment, and society (Ahrouch et al., 2017). These include supporting local production to meet community needs, strengthening resilience, and fostering sustainable job creation. Moreover, they promote regional identity, enhance economic value, and encourage sustainable modes of living and production (Ahrouch et al., 2017; Hammou & Lekbira, 2024).

1.1. Satisfaction

The marketing literature has extensively studied satisfaction. Customer satisfaction constitutes a common goal for all businesses (Szymanski & Henard, 2001; Elkandoussi & Omari, 2011). Its primary goal is to promote business growth and enhance market share, which will eventually lead to higher profitability (Chun & Nyam-Ochir, 2020). Oliver (1980) has defined customer satisfaction as the evaluation made after the purchase of a product. It is often

characterized as the degree to which the selected product meets or exceeds consumers' expectations. Based on the literature, three important conclusions emerge regarding satisfaction. First, satisfaction can be an emotional or cognitive response, with a varying intensity. Second, satisfaction can be associated with various aspects, including the purchase decision, the product itself or the consumption experience. Lastly, satisfaction is a temporally determined response that occurs following a specific situation (Giese & Cote, 2000). As consumers have become dissatisfied with conventional food produced through intensive agriculture (Gil et al., 2000), they have started placing greater emphasis on the origin and location of products. According to Aurier and Fort (2005), some consumers may be sensitive to the location of production, others see that local products provide guarantees of satisfaction, such as food safety (Ertus, 2021). Spielmann and Charters (2013) indicated that the authentic aspect of *terroir* products is positively related to satisfaction.

1.2. Trust

Trust has been extensively studied in the marketing literature (Tendeng et al., 2024). Considered as the foundation of relationships (Palmatier et al., 2006), trust has been shown to be essential, as no exchange system can function without it. From a marketing-oriented viewpoint, it serves as the core of any commercial exchange and forms the foundation for successful long-term relationships (Pennanen et al., 2007). It can only be achieved when the trusted party is perceived as having a positive image (Till & Nowak, 2000). Trust is a central concept in agri-food marketing. Trust in food conveys the idea that the brand functions reliably and ensures safety (Chaudhury & Holbrook, 2001). When it comes to food, consumers need extrinsic signals, such as labeling, to perceive it as trustworthy. The more those signals are credible the more consumers will trust them (Grunert et al., 2000; Brunsø et al., 2002). In the same vein, the *terroir* product labeling helps consumers perceive product as trustworthy (Belaid et al., 2024). These products are renowned for their unique production process and distinct origin (Cohen & Cohen, 2012), which help consumers perceive these products as trustworthy and reduce any doubts about them (Housni & Machrafi, 2024b). Belaid et al. (2024) stated that what matters is the story and the characteristics behind the *terroir*, as these elements have the ability to foster trust among consumers.

1.3. Enduring involvement

Involvement has been largely studied in the marketing literature. It is perceived as the relevance of something to a person, based on his values and needs (Zaichkowsky, 1985).

Consumer involvement can be assessed through the effort and the amount of time spent during the process of buying something (Laaksonen, 1994). Indeed, enduring involvement refers to the long-term relevance and the importance of a product category to someone (Ogbeide & Bruwer, 2013). Enduring involvement highlights the connection between a product and its reflection of an individual's values. It represents a person's identity, ego, and self-concept (Laurent & Kapferer, 1985). It reflects someone's commitment or engagement toward a specific product among others (McIntyre, 1989). According to Madrigal et al. (1992), involvement is a very important concept to be studied in consumer behavior, as people buy products based on their level of involvement. The higher their involvement, the more they will consider products that are relevant to their values and personalities. Previous research conducted by Bruwer et al. (2017); Charters et al. (2017); Ogbeide and Bruwer (2013) highlighted the importance of enduring involvement in terroir products. Charters et al. (2017) proposed that studying consumers' involvement with terroir products is necessary, as this area is ripe for further research. These products are purchased for what they represent to consumers (Ertus et al, 2019), requiring greater effort and time in the decision-making process. Terroir information is acquired through time, requiring a long period marked by enduring involvement Charters et al. (2017).

1.4. Purchase intention

Purchase intention is one of the most studied concepts in marketing literature, as it is considered an outcome of various factors (Martins et al., 2019). It is defined as the willingness of someone to buy a specific product (Wu et al., 2011), the possibility of buying something in the future (Dodds et al., 1991) or the attempt of someone to purchase a product to fulfil a need (Shao et al., 2004). It reflects a conscious plan formulated by an individual to strive toward purchasing something (Spears & Singh, 2004). New consumption trends have emerged, such as the use of green, sustainable, and socially responsible products. Today, consumers are increasingly gravitating toward these options, driven by growing concerns about the environment and their health (Ghvanidze et al., 2016; Laureti & Benedetti, 2018), values that are often upheld when purchasing terroir products (Ertus et al., 2019).

1.5. Conceptual model and hypotheses

Based on the literature, it exists a positive and significant relationship between enduring involvement and satisfaction (Tsai et al., 2011; Cheng et al., 2015). Given the importance of being actively involved in developing satisfactory feeling within consumers, it has been

studied in different contexts. It has been proven that the more a basketball fan is consistently involved in the game, the more likely he is to experience satisfaction (Laverie & Arnett, 2000). Additionally, individuals showing higher involvement in leisure activities tend to experience a sense of satisfaction each time they engage in such activities (Mudie et al., 2003). People who consistently attend festivals and are deeply involved in such activities tend to experience greater satisfaction with festival events compared to those who are less involved (Cheng et al., 2015). This relationship has also become a central focus in the realm of food culture. Craft beer and food festivals, renowned for their specific and traditional production processes, attract people seeking exciting and direct interactions with breweries. Studies have shown that individuals who frequently get involved in such experiences tend to report higher levels of satisfaction with craft beer and food festivals (Beckman et al., 2020). Terroir products, known for their unique characteristics, are primarily purchased and appreciated by individuals who value their virtues (Ertus et al., 2019). In this regard, it is reasonable to assume that individuals who are consistently involved in the consumption of terroir products will experience greater satisfaction compared to others. Such consumption brings satisfaction due to the high quality of the products, their health benefits, and their reduced environmental impact. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Consumer enduring involvement has a positive impact on consumers' satisfaction with terroir products.

The literature review highlighted a positive and significant relationship between satisfaction and trust (Martín et al., 2011; Darmawan, 2019). Trust is recognized as a positive outcome that emerges after multiple satisfactory experiences with a specific product or situation (Makaoui, 2014). Considered as an important link in food studies, the impact of satisfaction on trust highlighted important insights (Konuk, 2018; Al-Ansi et al., 2019; Shin & Yu, 2020). In this vein, past experiences with food consumption can influence consumers' evaluations of such products. According to Konuk (2018), organic food has the capacity to meet consumers' expectations, fostering satisfaction and positively building trust in these products. People with religious beliefs prefer to consume only halal food to avoid the guilt associated with consuming haram food. By respecting their beliefs and adhering to these dietary guidelines, they experience satisfaction, which fosters trust in these products (Al-Ansi et al., 2019). Given that terroir products are renowned for their superior quality and health benefits (Ertus, 2019), and that consumers value them for their benefits, they are likely to feel satisfied with their consumption, leading to positive outcomes, such as trust. Based on this, it is plausible to

expect that individuals who are satisfied with terroir products are more likely to trust them. Thus, we state the following hypothesis:

H2: Consumer satisfaction has a positive impact on consumers' trust in terroir products.

Based on the literature, trust exerts a positive effect on purchase intention, regardless of the studied context (Halim & Karsen, 2020; Husain et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2024). Regarding the food industry, this relationship highlighted significant results. Organic food labelling is perceived trustworthy by consumers and lead them to trust organic products (Sønderskov & Daugbjerg, 2011). This trust influences the likelihood of consumers to buy green food products (Nuttavuthisit & Thøgersen, 2017). Terroir products capture consumer attention, as they help alleviate distrust (Pichon, 2006; Ferrandi, 2013) caused by food crises and the effects of industrialization (Aprile et al., 2016). The terroir labelling help perceiving terroir products as trustworthy (Belaid et al., 2024). Indeed, consumers trust terroir products because they provide guarantees of quality and authenticity (Raif & Ait head, 2021) which lead to positive intentions (Ertus, 2024). Based on this, it is reasonable to expect that trust in terroir products will enhance consumers' purchase intention. Thereby, hypothesis H3 is posited:

H3: Consumer trust has a positive impact on consumers' purchase intention of terroir products.

All the hypotheses derived in this study are integrated into the conceptual framework illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure N°1 Conceptual framework

Source : Authors

2. Material and methods

This research seeks to validate a conceptual framework that integrates satisfaction, trust, and enduring involvement in the context of terroir products. To achieve this, data were collected using a combination of online and face-to-face surveys from 201 consumers of terroir products, employing the convenience method, a non-probabilistic sampling technique. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their participation was entirely

voluntary. Informed consent was obtained through an introductory statement on the survey form before participants proceeded to the questions. The characteristics of the sample are presented in **Table 1**.

Table N°1 Sample characteristics

Gender	%	Marital status	%	Occupation	%	Age	%	Income	%
Male	18.4%	Single	38.3%	Students	26.9%	20-29	41.3%	Less than 500	22.4%
Female	81.6%	Married	61.7%	Employees	25.9%	30-39	23.4%	500–1000	12.9%
				Executives	45.9%	40-49	20.9%	1001–1500	29.4%
				Others	1.3%	50 and above	14.4%	1501–2000	18.9%
								2001 and above	16.4%

Source : Authors

Moreover, we used scales measurement developed by Aurier and Fort (2005); Park et al. (2021); Fandos Herrera et al. (2011) and Pelet et al. (2020) to measure enduring involvement, satisfaction trust and purchase intention respectively (see **appendix 1**). All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5). All the measurement scales present good psychometric qualities (>0.7) and were used in terroir product and charity contexts. For the translation of the scales, we followed the guidelines of Vallerand (1989).

For data analysis, SPSS 27 and AMOS 23 software were used to conduct both exploratory and confirmatory analyses. Additionally, structural analysis was performed to evaluate the model's fit and validate the research hypotheses. To examine the mediation effect, the bootstrap procedure with Monte Carlo simulation (n=5000 iterations) was employed to determine the presence or absence of this effect.

3. Results

Initially, we conducted an Exploratory Analysis to identify latent variables and assess their reliability after purification. The results of Principal Component Analysis and Cronbach's alphas for the variables enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust and purchase intention are presented in the **Table 2**. Based on this table, all the PCA are valid, as indicated by the KMO values (>0.5), which demonstrate an acceptable factorial solution, and the significance of Bartlett's Test at the 5% level. All items exhibited satisfactory quality of representation, with values above the recommended threshold of 0.50, except for item TS_2, which showed a slightly lower extraction quality (0.486). Given its theoretical relevance and its proximity to the recommended threshold, TS_2 was initially retained for further examination. However, subsequent reliability and confirmatory factor analyses provided stronger evidence against its inclusion. Specifically, although the initial reliability analysis yielded an acceptable Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.759$), a comparative analysis revealed that removing TS_2 resulted in a substantial improvement in internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.826$). In addition, TS_2 exhibited a marginal standardized loading (0.50; see **Table 3**), further supporting its exclusion. In line with established methodological guidelines (Hair et al., 2019), TS_2 was therefore excluded from the final measurement model. Overall, the retained scales exhibited Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory reliability at the exploratory level.

Table N°2 Exploratory analyses outputs

PCA outputs				Cronbach's Alpha
Dimension	Items	Extraction	Eigenvalue	
Enduring involvement	INV_1	0.799	2.377	0.868
	INV_2	0.821		
	INV_3	0.757		
KMO = 0.732		Bartlett's Test of Sphericity = 0.000		
Cumulative Variance Explained = 79.235%				
PCA outputs				Cronbach's Alpha
Dimension	Items	Extraction	Eigenvalue	
Satisfaction	SAT_1	0.699	2.887	0.870

	INV_2	0.869
	INV_3	0.787
Satisfaction	SAT_1	0.775
	SAT_2	0.844
	SAT_3	0.734
	SAT_4	0.820
Trust	TS_1	0.867
	TS_2	0.500
	TS_3	0.802
Purchase intention	INT_1	0.647
	INT_2	0.876
	INT_3	0.869

Source : Authors

As shown in Table 4, enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust, and purchase intention demonstrate satisfactory reliability and validity at the confirmatory level, as all Jöreskog’s rho (composite reliability) values exceed the recommended threshold of 0.70 and all average variance extracted (AVE) values are above 0.50. Discriminant validity is further supported, as the square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the corresponding inter-construct correlations. Accordingly, the structural model was subsequently estimated to test the research hypotheses.

Table N°4 Confirmatory analyses outputs

Dimensions	Reliability (Jöreskog’ Rho)	Convergent validity	Discriminant validity			
			Enduring involvement	Satisfaction	Trust	Purchase intention
Enduring involvement	0.872	0.696	0.834	-	-	-
Satisfaction	0.872	0.630	0.443	0.794	-	-
Trust	0.830	0.711	-0.108	0.655	0.843	-
Purchase intention	0.846	0.651	0.218	0.141	0.104	0.806

Source : Authors

According to the results reported in Table 5 and Figure 2, the model demonstrates a satisfactory level of fit, as the parsimony, absolute, and incremental fit indices fall within the recommended thresholds. Although the RMSEA value is slightly above the conventional cut-off of 0.08, it remains within the acceptable range suggested in the literature for complex models (Hair et al., 2019). Furthermore, we found that the effects of enduring involvement on satisfaction, satisfaction on trust and trust on purchase intention are positive and significant at the 5% level, with C.R. values exceeding the recommended threshold (>2). Consequently, our hypotheses H1, H2 and H3 are statistically supported.

Table N°5 Structural analyses outputs

<i>Direct effects</i>			
Causal links	C.R.	P* value	Validation of hypotheses
H1: Enduring involvement → satisfaction	5.371	0.000*	Accepted
H2: Satisfaction → trust	6.625	0.000*	Accepted
H3: Trust → purchase intention	3.172	0.002*	Accepted
Sig: Significant *: P < 0.05 ns: not significant			
<i>Model fit indices:</i> GFI: 0.914; AGFI= 0.869; RMR: 0.069; RMSEA: 0.083; CFI: 0.944; IFI: 0.945; CMIN/DF: 2.371			
<i>Indirect effects</i>			
Causal links	Mediator variables	Standardized indirect effect	P* value
Enduring involvement → trust	Satisfaction	0.268	0.001
Satisfaction → purchase intention	Trust	0.159	0.006
Enduring involvement → purchase intention	Satisfaction and trust	0.069	0.004

Source : Authors

Figure N°2 Structural model

Source : Authors

According to our results, it is relevant to examine the mediating effects of satisfaction and trust. In this study, the Baron and Kenny (1986) causal steps approach is not appropriate, as the proposed model includes more than three variables and involves a serial mediation structure. Therefore, the mediation effects were assessed using a bootstrap procedure with Monte Carlo simulation, which is recommended for testing indirect effects.

The results reported in Table 5 indicate that both the direct and indirect effects of the three causal chains, enduring involvement → satisfaction → trust, satisfaction → trust → purchase intention, and enduring involvement → satisfaction → trust → purchase intention, are positive and statistically significant at the 5% level. These findings confirm that satisfaction and trust play a mediating role in these relationships, as all standardized indirect effects are significant and positive. Following Zhao et al. (2010), this pattern corresponds to a full mediation, indicating that the relationships among enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust, and purchase intention operate through satisfaction and trust in a sequential manner.

4. Discussion

This research validates a theoretical model integrating enduring involvement, satisfaction, trust, and purchase intention toward terroir products. To our knowledge, the novelty of this study lies in shifting the focus from product-related attributes to the psychological and relational mechanisms underlying consumer behavior. While previous research on terroir products has primarily adopted a cognitive approach emphasizing product attributes, this study highlights the role of enduring involvement and relational constructs in shaping purchase intention. By adopting a process-based perspective, it provides a deeper understanding of how consumers develop relational mechanisms, such as satisfaction and trust, through psychological processes—particularly enduring involvement—thereby offering added value to the existing literature.

4.1. Theoretical contribution

From this standpoint, the examination of the structural model allowed to validate all the hypotheses and highlighted two mediators, satisfaction and trust as indicated by Setiobudi (2021) and Ayyub et al. (2021) respectively. Results highlighted the positive impact of enduring involvement on satisfaction toward terroir products. Constant involvement enables consumers to maintain a consistent internal psychological state shaped by emotions of excitement and interest, leading to satisfaction derived from experiencing these positive emotions repeatedly. These results are in good agreement with earlier research by (Beckman

et al., 2020). Indeed, we found that satisfaction has a positive effect on trust toward terroir products. Consistently experiencing satisfaction from consuming and purchasing terroir products reinforces their trustworthiness among consumers. Repeated satisfaction signifies that the products maintain the same quality and uphold their values. This perception encourages consumers to place greater trust in terroir products. Numerous investigations, including (Konuk, 2018; Al-Ansi et al., 2019) have previously corroborated this observation. Finally, trust has a positive effect on the purchase intention of terroir products. Trusting something leads to positive outcomes. In this case, when consumers perceive terroir products as trustworthy and consistently delivering the same values over time, they are more likely to consider purchasing them. Confidence in a product—combined with the belief that it offers advantages such as protecting health through natural ingredients and providing superior quality—encourages consumers to buy these products to benefit from their inherent value. These findings are consistent with previous research by (Ertus, 2024).

4.2. Managerial contribution

Our results offer significant insights for marketers to implement effective strategies concerning terroir products. Thereby, practitioners and marketers should develop strategies aimed at fostering consumers' commitment to enduring involvement, enhancing satisfaction, building trust in terroir products, and encouraging purchase consideration. Accordingly, we provide the following recommendations for producers and cooperatives, distributors and retailers, public authorities and institutions, as well as tourism and gastronomy stakeholders. Producers and cooperatives are encouraged to use official labels for terroir products, such as LA, IGP, and AOP, to enhance their credibility. Certification by established organizations can increase consumers' perception of terroir products as trustworthy, ultimately driving their purchase decisions. In addition, producers and cooperatives should showcase consumers' experiences with terroir products through advertising, as storytelling can enhance trust and evoke positive emotions associated with these products. Terroir products are often sought after by socially conscious consumers. Therefore, we recommend targeting Gen Z, a generation known for its strong involvement in sustainable and responsible consumption behaviors. Moreover, implementing digital traceability tools, such as QR codes providing information on product origin, production processes, and producer identity, could enhance transparency and strengthen consumer trust in terroir products.

Distributors and retailers are advised to leverage immersive marketing techniques, such as virtual reality, to help consumers imagine a prolonged post-consumption experience. Enabling consumers to envision the potential positive effects of terroir products on their health may enhance satisfaction with their choice and foster a deeper involvement with these products. Moreover, distributors and retailers should promote terroir products through social media using sponsored advertisements in order to reach a wider audience, especially individuals who lack physical access to these products, thereby increasing purchase intention. Partnering with trustworthy influencers can enhance the perception of terroir products as reliable and credible. When these influencers express their satisfaction with terroir products and endorse their trust in their ability to protect both health and the environment, they can effectively foster satisfaction and trust among consumers, thereby strengthening their purchase intention.

Public authorities and institutions are encouraged to implement educational campaigns that emphasize the importance of terroir products in valuing local cultural, gastronomic, and touristic heritage. Such initiatives can foster enduring involvement by encouraging long-term commitment to supporting local products. In addition, establishing permanent stands for terroir products in highly frequented locations is recommended, as their constant availability may encourage long-term purchasing habits and strengthen consumers' connection with terroir products.

Tourism and gastronomy stakeholders are encouraged to create tourist routes dedicated to terroir products by highlighting local cultural and culinary heritage, which can strengthen consumers' purchase intention. Furthermore, collaborating with renowned chefs to promote the use of terroir products is recommended. By involving chefs in culinary events and tasting experiences, consumers can directly experience dishes prepared with terroir products, which may increase satisfaction, strengthen trust, and ultimately enhance purchase intention.

4.3 Limitations and future avenues

Our research provides significant insights to the literature; however, it has some limitations that should be addressed in future studies. First, we tested terroir products in general. Future research might focus on examining a specific category of terroir product to determine whether the results vary depending on the product type. Second, we used only psychological and relational variables. For future avenues, we may add attitudinal or experiential variables as: attitude, emotional response, variety seeking etc. Also, we may add moderator variables such as: skepticism, product origin, etc. Third, we examined purchase intention as the model's

output. Future studies could explore the actual purchase to gain deeper insights into the motives influencing purchase decisions. Fourth, social desirability bias may have influenced respondents' answers; future studies could include control measures or indirect questioning techniques to limit this effect. Fifth, this study focuses on the Tunisian context, providing context-specific insights. Future research may build on these findings by examining other geographic settings to allow for cross-cultural analysis. Finally, the cross-sectional design of the study restricts causal interpretation; future research could adopt longitudinal or experimental designs to better capture causal relationships.

Appendix 1. Research measurement scales

1) Enduring involvement (Aurier & Fort, 2005)

INV_1: Terroir food products are for me of great importance

INV_2: I consider that terroir food product is something important to me

INV_3: I'm highly motivated by terroir food products

2) Satisfaction (Park et al., 2021)

SAT_1: Overall, I am satisfied with my decision to buy terroir products

SAT_2: I believe that I did the right thing in buying terroir products

SAT_3: Satisfied is a good description of how I feel about terroir products

SAT_4: I am so glad that I purchased terroir products

3) Trust (Fandos Herrera et al., 2011)

TS_1: I think that terroir food products is trustworthy

TS_2: I trust in the recommendations of my usual retailer of terroir food products

TS_3: The quality of terroir food products is trustworthy

4) Purchase intention (Pelet et al., 2020)

INT_1: I will definitely buy terroir food products in the near future.

INT_2: It is likely that I will buy terroir food products in the near future.

INT_3: I am planning to buy terroir food products in the near future.

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